

THE PECULIARITIES OF DEVELOPING PHONETIC COMPETENCE

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ABSTRACT

The article explores the features of teaching the pronunciation part of speech in the conditions of contact of three or more languages. These conditions are referred to as artificial multilingualism. The goal of teaching phonetics in artificial multilingualism, as well as in teaching the first foreign language, is to form phonetic competence, which includes specific skills (auditory and pronunciation), knowledge and skills.

Keywords: phonological signs, articulatory base, foreign language accent, phonetic skill, phonetic competence, artificial multilingualism, pronunciation.

In the conditions of linguistic lyceums, linguistic universities and faculties, in the study of foreign languages, a situation of artificial multilingualism develops, by which we mean proficiency in two or more foreign languages as a result of purposeful learning. This type of multilingualism is characterized by “asymmetric communicative competence in relation to languages in contact and the controlled nature of its formation”.

Within the framework of the competence-based approach, the goal of teaching a foreign language (first, second, etc.) is communicative competence, which is the basis for the development of multilingual competence. Multilingual competence should be understood as a network of complex relationships of knowledge and linguistic experience that a person acquires gradually and in stages. An integral component responsible for the competent design of an utterance is linguistic competence, consisting of phonetic, lexical, and grammatical.

Phonetic competence includes phonetic skills, knowledge and ability to perceive and reproduce the following elements:

- phonemes and their implementation in a specific context (allophones);
- phonetic signs that distinguish some phonemes from others (sonority, nasality, labialization, etc.);

- prosody; the phenomena of assimilation at the moment of articulation, reduction of unstressed vowels, phrasal stress and rhythm; intonation, etc.

The importance of the pronunciation side of speech is due to its entry into all types of speech activity. For example, as a component of speaking, pronunciation can make words easier or more difficult for the listener to recognize. The communicative significance of the pronunciation side of speaking is to give clarity to the oral text. In listening, the pronunciation side of speech is directly involved in the process of perception. If the student perceives the spoken text incorrectly, he has difficulties in identifying, understanding and interpreting the text, i.e. insufficient level of phonetic competence makes it difficult to understand speech by ear.

In the field of phonetics, the influence of the native language on the studied foreign language is more pronounced than at other levels of the language. Difficulties in mastering the sounds of a foreign language are explained by the interference of the native language.

O. A. Yamshchikova understands phonetic interference as “violation (distortion) of the secondary and subsequent language system and its norms as a result of interaction in the speaker’s mind of phonetic systems and pronunciation systems of two or more languages”. There is an interference of auditory and pronunciation skills formed on the basis of interacting systems. Pronunciation is the most automated area of the language. In mastering pronunciation, skill plays a decisive role. Phonetic skills provide the ability to correctly perceive the audible sounds of foreign language speech and reproduce them adequately to the existing norm.

The depth and amount of interference can vary. The result of phonetic interference is a foreign language accent, which is characterized as "substitution of unknown sounds and unusual combinations of sounds with their own familiar ones and rethinking of words with their morphological composition and their meanings according to the skills of their language".

For clarity, you can use articulation schemes. Thus, there is an acquaintance with almost all the features of the articulatory base in practice.

Having disassembled the alphabet, students receive memorization as homework. In the next lesson, the alphabet is checked and corrected. Further, the theoretical material on the features of the articulatory base is analyzed. Since in practice, students have already become familiar with the new articulatory base, the theoretical material is perceived by them in a natural way.

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